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**PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE ORGANIZATION
OF EDUCATION**

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Annotation: The material of this conference reflects the role of pedagogical technologies in education and its content. In particular, education and the forms of technology in it are analyzed. The application of educational technologies to the teaching process and the importance of working in it individually, in groups and in the team is analyzed in general.

Keywords: Educational technologies, pedagogical technologies, educational content, organizational form.

The modern high development of science, technology and production automatically puts new social demands on the agenda. Among these social requirements, society is of great importance, and the force that drives the development of industries based on it is the training of qualified personnel, the improvement of the system aimed at this goal. Although the need for the training of qualified personnel arose in the early stages of the development of the industrial sector, when manufacturing enterprises appeared, it still does not lose its relevance.

The main reasons for this are the emergence of new areas, specializations, the need to train personnel in accordance with the social, economic and cultural development of society, professional knowledge, skills and abilities of specialists in a changing, rapidly changing era. the formation of a need for continuous improvement, as well as an increased demand for the ability to cope with strong competition in the labor market as a specialist.

The problem of studying non-traditional forms and methods in teaching a foreign language. It was considered in the works of I.P.Podlasova, V.A.Slastenina, I.F.Isaeva and similar methodologists and psychologists. Non-standard forms and methods of education are considered to be the process of education, upbringing and development of the student. This approach makes it possible to diversify the student's life, increase motivation to study science, and develop the intellectual and emotional sphere of activity.

The form of education or pedagogical form is a field that ensures the stable, complete organization of the pedagogical process in the unity of all components, and the pedagogical form is the stable, complete organization of the pedagogical

process in the unity of all components. The method of expressing the content of the form, therefore, is considered as its carrier. The effectiveness of the educational process increases the use of different forms of education in foreign language classes.

The term "form of organization of learning" refers to the specific type of this lesson. The most complete forms of organization of educational activities of students are M.D.Vinogradova, V.K.Dyachenko, V.V.Kotova, M.N.Skatkina, I.M.Cheredova and others considered in their works. The authors agree that the interaction between teaching and learning is carried out in organizational forms. The authors agree that the interaction between teaching and learning is carried out in organizational forms. Thanks to the form, the content becomes visible, adapts to the use. Any form consists of the same components: goals, principles, learning content, methods and means. Language classes have direct and indirect organizational forms of learning, reflecting the nature of communication between its participants. Direct training is carried out in group or individual form. Mediated learning takes place without personal contact between the teacher and the student, mainly through written language or substitute means. Organizational forms regulate (determine) the relationship between the individual and the team in learning, the level of activity of students in educational and cognitive activity, the nature of its management by the teacher. The form of training can be different and depends on the intensity of communication in the learning process. Thus, the student is both the subject of educational and cognitive activity and the subject of indirect (remote) communication, for example, through a book or direct communication with a teacher or other students. Accordingly, individual, pair, group and frontal forms of educational work are known.

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